

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE CAUCASUS ISSUE IN THE FOREIGN POLICY OF THE OTTOMAN-SAFAVID-RUSSIAN STATES IN THE FIRST HALF OF THE 18TH CENTURY

Seyidova Sevinj Mammad

Prof. Dr.,

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

ORCID: 0009-0003-8839-3506

Abstract

The article examines issues related to the foreign policy of the Ottoman-Safavid-Russian states in the second half of the 18th century. In this study, the author argues that the implementation of the Caucasus policy in the 18th century occupied a special place in the geopolitical rivals, the Ottoman, Russian and Safavid states. The Caucasus region, located at the junction of Europe and Asia, where land and water routes to Central Asia, the Near and Middle East passed, played a very important role in the policies of the parties fighting each other. Great Britain, France and other Western states also actively intervened in the internal affairs of the Caucasus.

Keywords: Caucasus issue, foreign policy, competition, Ottoman, Safavid, Russian empire

Introduction

The Caucasus problem had complex features. The role of the Caucasus in the policy of the Ottoman Empire was noticeably felt. This policy can be divided into the following stages according to its importance for the Ottoman Empire and the peoples of the Caucasus:

1) The last quarter of the 15th century - the end of the 17th century;

2) From the Treaty of Istanbul to the Treaty of Sulak (1700-1721);

3) From the accession of Dagestan to Russia to the collapse of the rule of Nader Shah (1722-1747);

1. The collapse of the Ottoman foreign policy in the Caucasus

Each of the above stages was distinguished by its own characteristics, the number of driving forces, goals and objectives, methods and means of achieving them. The first stage (1475-1699), which began with the occupation of the Black Sea fortresses (Feodosia, Sunjik, Taman, Temruk, Azak-Sea of Azov) by the Ottomans and the establishment of control over the Crimea, laid the foundation for the Caucasian policy of the Ottoman Empire and envisaged the solution of the following issues:

1) Taking control of the route along which the pilgrimage to Mecca was carried out and leading to Kabarda;

2) Attacking Astrakhan, Kazan and Central Asia from the North Caucasus in order to unite with the Muslim peoples of the East;

3) Surrounding this state from the north in order to successfully fight the Safavids;

4) Blocking the Russians' path to the Caucasus, preventing them from expanding southward;

5) To force the peoples of the Caucasus to submit to the Ottoman Empire, to strengthen the influence of Islam there.

The Ottomans were unable to achieve these goals. First, because in the second half of the 17th century, the Ottoman ruling circles were preoccupied with the conquest of large territories in Europe, Asia, and North Africa; second, in connection with the crisis that began in

the Ottoman Empire in the 1780s and 1790s, the Ottomans suffered a series of heavy defeats at the hands of the European coalition states and Russia, as a result of which they lost Hungary, Transylvania, Slovenia, Right-Bank Ukraine, Podolia, Morea, Dalmatia, and some islands of Azov; third, it was at this stage of the Ottoman Empire's Caucasian policy that its geopolitical rival, the Safavid state, emerged. According to the Treaty of Qasr-e Shirin of 1639, western Georgia and Iraq were considered the territory of the Ottoman Empire [2,157]. The Ottomans' situation was further complicated by the fact that from the middle of the 16th century, Tsarist Russia, along with the Safavids, began to oppose the Ottoman Empire's Caucasian policy. Russia achieved the annexation of Astrakhan in 1556, Kabarda in 1557, and the Turkish fortress of Azov in 1700.

Thus ended the first phase of the Ottoman Empire's Caucasian policy, and the second phase, covering the period from the Treaty of Istanbul in 1700 to the Treaty of Sulak in 1721, began. At this stage, the Ottomans directed the offensive vector of their foreign policy from Europe to the Caucasus, hoping that they would be able to compensate for what they had lost there by occupying the territories of the North Caucasus and southern Russian lands. According to some reports, from the beginning of the 17th century until the Sulak Treaty, Ottoman-Crimean attacks on Kabarda and the southern Russian provinces took place almost without interruption in 1699-1701, 1703-1704, 1707-1708, 1710-1717, 1720-1721.

The most important of the main events characterizing the Caucasian policy of the Ottoman Empire and its consequences for the peoples of the region and for the Ottoman Empire itself was the defeat of the 40,000-strong army of Kaplan Geray Khan in the Battle of Kanjal in Kabarda in 1708. In order to take possession of the Caucasian territories up to the Safavid border, the Ottoman Empire and the Crimean Khanate appealed to the rulers of Dagestan and Kabarda. Some of them went over to the Ottoman side under the leadership of the Kabarda prince Islam bey Misostav, who was from the Baksan community.

At the same time, uprisings began in the Safavid state - in Dagestan and Shirvan. This dealt a blow to the Safavid rule in the Caucasus. In the current situation, A.P. Volynsky's campaign to the Terek was very successful for Russia. As a result of this campaign, the Russian-Ottoman Sulak agreement was signed, according to which Kabarda was considered to be mainly within the sphere of influence of the Ottoman Empire. In August 1721, the Dagestan and Shirvan rebels, led by the Khan of Qazigumukh Surkhay Khan and Davud Bey from Mushkur, captured Shamakhi, abolished Safavid rule there, killed 300 Russian merchants, and also plundered their goods worth 1 to 2 million rubles. Then they turned to the Ottoman Empire for subordination [6,99]. Thus, the Shamakhi massacre of 1721 gave impetus to the re-strengthening of the Caucasian policy of Russia and the Ottoman Empire. The threat of Dagestan and Shirvan falling into the hands of the Ottoman Empire became real. All these factors led Peter I to march to the Caspian Sea in 1722, which marked the beginning of the third stage of the Ottoman Empire's Caucasian policy.

2. Ottoman-Safavid-Russian competition for the Caucasus

This stage of the Ottoman Empire's Caucasian policy, especially its part related to Dagestan, was the most important compared to the previous and subsequent stages. The characteristic feature of the Ottoman Empire's policy at this stage was not only the use of diplomatic, military, political and other acquired means, but also the use of the Sunni sect of Islam to achieve its geopolitical goals [5,6]. After Peter I's campaign to the Caspian coast, Russian troops occupied the Caspian coastal provinces, including Dagestan, up to the Agrakhan Gulf and the Minakand River [4,19].

During this period, the Ottoman Empire also became more active. As a result of the Petersburg Treaty of 1723, Dagestan, the Caspian coastal provinces of Azerbaijan, Gilan, Mazandaran and Astrabad passed into the hands of Russia. The Ottoman Empire was dissatisfied with this treaty. England and France supported the Ottoman Empire. That is why in 1724 the Russian and Ottoman Empires signed the Istanbul Treaty.

The complete weakening of the Safavid state in the 30s of the 18th century led to the emergence of Nadir Khan Afshar on the political scene. In order to return the historical territories of the Safavid state, Nadir began a struggle against the Ottoman Empire. For this purpose, Nadir Khan approached the Russian Empire. On January 21, 1732, he signed the Rasht Treaty with Russia, and on March 10, 1735, the Ganja Treaty, according to which the Russians returned the Safavid lands occupied by the Russians in the Caucasus. However, the Russians did not completely liberate the North Caucasus, but withdrew their troops to the Terek and remained in Gizlar. The fact that the Russians remained in Gizlar, as well as the fact that Nadir Khan Afshar was able to take back the historical Safavid lands from Russia, angered the Ottoman Empire, and they sent the troops of the Crimean Khanate, which was subordinate to the Ottoman Empire, to march on the Caucasus. In 1733, the Crimean Fati Geray attacked the Kuban, Kabarda, Chechnya and Dagestan with an army of 25,000. This was followed in the summer of 1734 by Nadir Khan's first campaign against Shamakhi, which ended

with Surkhay Khan's hasty departure from Shamakhi and flight to Avaristan [1,206].

In 1735, the Ottoman sultan ordered the Crimean Khan to march on the Caucasus. The Crimean Khan Qafan Geray arrived in the Caucasus with an 80,000-strong cavalry. However, he was stopped by the troops of the Shirvan Beylerbey Ali Khan [3,194-200].

In 1735, Nadir Khan also made a second campaign against Shirvan, and by the end of the same year, the Ottoman troops were completely expelled from the Fore Caucasus. The Ottoman Empire, which suffered defeat in the Caucasus, started a war with Russia in 1735-1739 with the instigation and support of Great Britain and France. The Russo-Ottoman War ended with the victory of Russia and the Treaty of Belgrade. However, the neutrality of Kabarda was maintained in the Treaty of Belgrade, which meant the loss of Kabarda for Russia.

During Nadir Shah's campaign in Dagestan in 1741-1743, the rulers here were supported by the Ottoman Empire with various means (money and gifts). In 1747, Nadir Shah was assassinated as a result of an assassination attempt and the state he created completely collapsed, which led to the reactivation of the Ottoman Empire in the Caucasus. The Russian government, which did not want the Ottoman Empire to strengthen its influence in the Caucasus, also took its own measures. Unlike the Ottoman Empire, Russia, which had strengthened its positions in Europe, was able to act more decisively in the Caucasus. Russia began to present itself as the patron of the Caucasian peoples.

Conclusion

Thus, the events that took place from the time of Nadir Shah Afshar's campaign in Dagestan to the consolidation of Russia's position in the region showed that, despite some tactical changes, Caucasian policy remained the focus of the Ottomans. During this period, Russia became closer to the rulers of the Caucasus, especially Dagestan. The Ottoman Empire, on the other hand, sometimes sought mutual relations with Nadir Shah, and sometimes tried to weaken him. Russia, taking advantage of this rivalry, took the first steps to strengthen its position in the region.

References

1. Bakikhanov A. On the Campaigns of Shah Nadir in Dagestan // Kavkaz. 1964. No. 18. – Pp. 62-82.
2. Bobylev V.S. Russia's Foreign Policy in the Era of Peter the Great. – Moscow: Publishing House of the University of Friendship of Peoples, 1990. – 116 p.
3. Russia's Treaties with the East, Political and Trade / Compiled by T.D. Yuzefovich. St. Petersburg: Bakst Printing House, 1869. – 294 p.
4. Kabardino-Russian Relations in the 16th – 18th Centuries. Documents and Materials. // Compiled by V.M. Bukalova. In 2 volumes. Moscow: Publishing House of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1957. Vol. 2. – 532 p.
5. Meyer M.S. The Ottoman Empire in the 18th Century: Features of the Structural Crisis. Moscow: Nauka, 1991. 257 p.
6. Potto, V.A. Two Centuries of the Terek Cossacks (1557-1801). In 2 volumes. Vladikavkaz: Regional Administration Press, 1912. Vol. 1 – 116 p.; Vol. 2 – 247 p.